

ASSOCIATION OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA WITH FEBRILE CONVULSIONS IN THE PEDIATRIC POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

Background: Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) in children aged between 6 and 60 months increases susceptibility to febrile seizures. This association highlights the intricate interplay between nutritional status and neurological susceptibility in young children. Iron is essential for cognitive development and neurological function, becomes critically deficient in many children due to inadequate dietary intake or absorption issues. Literature has shown that IDA is significantly associated with febrile convulsions. However, controversial data has been observed in literature also. Therefore, we conducted this study to get evidence of association of IDA with febrile convulsions in local population. **Objective:** To estimate the link between iron deficiency anemia and febrile seizures in six- to sixty-month-old or older children.

Material & Method

Study Design: Case control.

Setting: Department of Pediatrics, Isra University Hospital, Hyderabad

Duration: 06 months i.e., 31-7-2023 to 31-1-2024

Data Collection: After meeting selection criteria 68 children were enrolled. These children were categorized into two groups which include cases patient of any sex having a diagnosis of febrile convulsions who developed iron deficiency anemia; and controls patient of either sex withni febrile convulsions along without anemia. This was followed by a blood sample for serum ferritin and Hb. Reports were reviewed and IDA was categorized. Data were registered & information processed by SPSS version 25. Odds Ratio was calculated, and then 2x2 contingency table was created to assess association between IDA with febrile convulsions. $OR > 1$ was taken as significant.

Results: The average age was 6.53 ± 3.71 years, including 26(38.24%) males and 42(61.76%) females in the study cohort. IDA was seen in 22(64.7%) patients in case and 11(32.4%) patients in control group. Getting odds of IDA among cases in comparison to controls is 1.94. i.e., p -value=0.008 & $OR=1.94[1.16-3.26]$.

Conclusion: The prevalence of IDA (iron deficiency anemia) is a much higher in children with febrile convulsion than children without hematological anomaly among age group 6 to 60 months.

Keywords: Iron deficiency Anemia, Febrile Convulsion, Children

INTRODUCTION

Seizures occurring in association with fever, including simple febrile convulsions, constitute the most frequent seizure disorder in children aged 6 and 60 months without evidence of central nervous system infection. This disease occurs in ~ 2.5% of children, being most prevalent at approximately one to one and a half years of age.¹ Febrile convulsion have been the subject of much research over the last 20 years and there is now a solid evidence base that clinicians can use to determine risks following such encounters.²

Iron deficiency is great micronutrient disorder prevalent worldwide and is easily preventable and treatable. Iron deficiency is among the top three of “hidden hunger (Iron, Iodine, and Vitamin A: sub-clinical deficiency without signs)”.²⁵ With approximately one fifth of children of the world living in developing world foci including 60–80% in some regions like African continent this is by far the predominantly single micro nutrient deficient.³ Iron deficiency has also been suggested to be one of the predisposing factors for seizure by decreasing threshold for febrile seizure⁶⁴. Several researches have attempted to define the correlation between IDA and febrile seizure but a variety of findings have been reported.⁴

In a study conducted in southern Iran, IDA was found to be significantly related with febrile convulsions i.e. 56.6% cases vs 24.8% controls and the difference between these two groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).⁵ A similar study performed in Pakistan revealed significant relation between IDA and febrile convulsions i.e. 59% cases and 26% controls with a $p < 0.05$.⁶

A Korean study reported that low iron, determined by a serum ferritin level of under 30 ng/mL, was three times as common in children with febrile seizures (49.2%) as compared to the control group (16.9%). The authors propose that iron deficiency itself, regardless of anaemia per se increases the odds of developing febrile seizures.⁷

The objective is to find out correlation of IDA in paediatric patients with febrile convulsion. We know that according to literature, IDA is highly-linked with febrile fits [7]. However, controversial findings can be found in literature where there is not any significant effect on febrile convulsions with iron deficiency (ref # 7 & 8). So, we want to do this study to have evidence of link of febrile convulsions with iron deficiency among our children presented suffering from febrile

convulsion so that preventive action for folic acid deficiency can be taken including iron supplementation and feeding advice. In addition, correct reporting and result salvage will also help our paediatricians and policy makers to grow our understanding of better treatment practices. Additionally, the data can be used by policy makers to develop targeted public health interventions that aim to prevent childhood illnesses and promote healthy behaviours. For instance, if the data demonstrates that geographic group is at higher risk for IDA, policy makers can implement targeted education and screening programs to address this disparity.

OBJECTIVE:

To estimate the link between iron deficiency anemia and febrile seizures in six- to sixty-month-old or older children.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Design: Case control study

Setting: Department of Pediatrics, Isra University Hospital, Hyderabad.

Duration of Study: The duration of the study was from 31-7-2023 to 31-1-2024

Sample Size: Sample size was determined using the WHO sample size calculator yielding 34 individuals per study group, making a total of 68. The sample size was calculated with a study power of 80%, $\alpha = 5\%$ significance and proportions set at an assumed prevalence of iron deficient anaemia being 56.6% for the case and 24.8% in control group respectively based on previous local studies.⁵

Sample Method: Participants were enrolled through a consecutive non-probability sampling approach.

Sample Selection:

Inclusion Criteria: Children aged between six and sixty months of either gender who presented to the emergency department with a body temperature of 100°F or higher were included in the study.

- **Case:** Patients of either gender diagnosed with febrile convulsions and meeting the criteria for iron deficiency anemia, as defined in the operational guidelines, were classified as cases.

- **Control:** Patients of either gender who experienced febrile convulsions but did not meet the criteria for iron deficiency anemia were classified as controls.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children already taking or taken iron supplement, blood transfusion within 3 months.
- Children with definite neurological illness, presence of ventriculoperitoneal shunt and history of head trauma.
- Children with malnutrition (<2SD as per WHO classification), developmental delay, having metabolic diseases, recurrent iron deficiency anemia (within 6 months)
- Children with thalassemia, abnormal clotting profile (INR>2) or other blood disorders associated with anemia.

Data Collection Process:

Informed consent was taken from patients at the beginning of the trial and approval by ethics committee had already been made. Sixty-eight eligible children were recruited from the Pediatric Emergency Department. Written informed consent was provided by the parents or caretakers. Relevant demographic and clinical characteristics, such as name, age, weight (kg), sex, height (cm), duration of fever, body temperature at enrollment point of care, place of residence, and socioeconomic status were recorded for every participant. Then the child was divided in two groups i.e., cases patient of either gender with diagnosis of febrile convulsions or controls patient of either gender with fever but without convulsions. A 3cc disposable syringe was used to draw the blood sample aseptically. All samples were transferred to the hospital laboratory for serum ferritin and hemoglobin level assessment. Reports were reviewed and grades were documented. Iron Deficiency Anemia (IDA) was defined based on the operational definition with hemoglobin levels of 11 g/dL or lower, and a serum ferritin level less than 30 ng/mL. Patients with IDA were treated according to standard treatment regimens. A structured performa (attached) was used to record the relevant information.

Data Analysis:

Data was analysed on SPSS software version 25.

The Shapiro-Wilk test was used for the testing of normality of continuous variables. Descriptive statistics (mean, median, and standard deviation) was computed for the quantitative variables such as age of the child, weight of the child, duration of fever in days at which Hb measurement was made, and serum ferritin level. Categorical data such as gender, locality, socioeconomic status and IDA were described in terms of frequency and percentages. Group comparisons were made using Chi-square test and p -value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. 2x2 contingency table created to determine odds ratio for association of IDA and febrile convulsions. $OR > 1$ was taken as significant. Age, sex, weight, place of residence and socioeconomic status were stratified along with duration of fever. After post-stratification, by chi-square test groups were compared with significant level of p -value of less than or equal to 0.05 and odds ratio was calculated from generated 2x2 contingency table to estimate association between IDA and febrile convulsions for each stratum. $OR > 1$ was taken as significant.

RESULTS:

This study included 68 patients. The average age of these participants was 6.53 ± 3.71 years, ranging from 6 months to 60 months old). Table 1

In the control and case groups, the mean of ages was 5.09 ± 3.54 years and 7.97 ± 3.33 years for the participants, respectively ($p = 0.001$) (Table 2).

Of the 68 participants, 26 (38.2%) were men and 42 (61.8%) were women, yielding a male-to-female ratio of 0.6:1 (Figure 1). In the case and control groups there were respectively 13 (38.2%) male subjects, and no significant differences in sex distributions of cases vs controls were observed ($p > 0.999$) (Table 3).

The average weight of the children was 15.09 ± 6.97 kg and the mean duration of fever was 4.59 ± 1.63 days (Table 4).

The mean weight was 12.65 ± 6.52 kg in the case group and it was 17.53 ± 6.61 kg in control group showing a significant difference ($p = 0.003$). The mean fever time was 5.00 ± 1.48 days in the case group, and 4.17 ± 1.69 days in the control group, which were significantly different ($p = 0.036$) (Table 5).

In our study 33(48.5%) patients belonged to rural area while 35(51.5 %) from urban area. Table 6

In group 15(44.1%) were from rural area and in group controls 18(52.9%) were from rural area with

p-value of 0.467 (statistically insignificant). Table 7

33.82% (23) patients were low SES, 35.29% (24) patients belonged to middle and about thirty-point eighty eight percent (21) were from high group of SES in our study. Figure - 2

In the present study, 8 (23.5%) and 15 (44.1%) subjects in the case and control groups were categorized as low socioeconomic status (SES). This difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.199$) (Table 8), with SES stratified by monthly income according to the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2020) Household Integrated Economic Survey (HIES).

The mean hemoglobin was 10.34 ± 2.43 g/dL in the case group and it was 11.93 ± 2.41 g/dL in the control group, that were statistically significant ($p = 0.009$). In addition, the mean serum ferritin concentration was lower in the case group (26.17 ± 6.67 ng/mL) than that in the control group (33.57 ± 9.19 ng/mL) ($p = 0.013$) (Table 10).

Altogether, 33 participants (48.5%) had iron deficiency anemia (IDA) in total population shown in Figure 3. In the case group, IDA was found in 22 (64.7%) cases and 11 (32.4%) controls. The risk for development of IDA was found to be 1.94 times greater in the case group compared with controls ($p = 0.008$, OR = 1.94 [1.16-3.26]) (Table 10).

When age-stratified ≤ 6 years-old, 17 (68%) of the cases vs. 2(14.3%) in controls have IDA [OR = 12.75 (2.29-70.96)]. For participants >6 years, 5 (55.6%) cases and 9 (45%) controls had IDA OR = 1.53 (0.31-7.43).

By sex, 9 (69.2%) male cases were IDA compared to 4 (30.8%) control [OR = 5.06 (0.95-26.77)]. In females, involved in 13 (61.9%) cases and 7 (33.3%) controls [OR = 3.25 description (0.92-11.51)] were the difference between case and control group participants affected (Table 12).

On weight-based analysis, children ≤ 15 kg had a total of 17 (68%) cases with IDA and 2 controls (14.3%) [OR = 12.75 (2.29-70.96)]. In >15 Kg children, 5 cases (55.6%) and 9 controls (45%) suffered from IDA [OR = 1.53(0.31-7.43)] (Table 13).

Regarding the duration of fever, in those with fever ≤ 4 days 11 (73.3%) had IDA and 8 had no IDA [OR = 3.78(0.87-16.32)]. Eleven (57.9%) cases and 3 (20%) controls were impacted for fever >4 days [OR = 5.50 (1.15-26.14)] (Table 14).

In rural residents, 10 cases (66.7%) and 8 controls (44.4%) had IDA [OR = 2.50 (0.60-10.34)]. The affected and control numbers in urban subjects were 12 (63.2%) and 3 (18.8%) [OR = 7.73 (1.55-35.47)] respectively (Table 15).

When the data were stratified according to SES, low SES subjects had 5 cases (62.5%) and 4 controls (26.7%) with IDA [OR = 4.58 (0.73-28.64)]. Among individuals of middle socio-economic status (SES), 7 cases (50%) and 5 controls (50%) were exposed [OR = 1.00 (0.19-5.07)]. For high SES children, 10 cases (83.3%) and two controls (22.2%) had IDA [OR = 17.50 (1.97-155.59)] (Tables 16A & B).

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of age (years)

Age (Years)	N	68
	Mean	6.53
	Standard Deviation	3.71
	Minimum	1.00
	Maximum	12.00

Table Comparison of age (years) between study groups

	Study Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value
Age (Years)	Case	34	5.09	3.54	0.001
	Control	34	7.97	3.33	

Figure - 1 Frequency distribution of gender

Table 3 Comparison of gender between study groups

		Study Groups		Total	p-value
		Case	Control		
Gender	Male	13	13	26	>0.999
		38.2%	38.2%	38.2%	
Female	21	21	42		
	61.8%	61.8%	61.8%		
Total		34	34	68	
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Table 4 Descriptive statistics of weight and duration of fever (days)

	n	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Weight (Kg)	68	15.09	6.97	5.00	28.00
Duration of fever (days)	68	4.59	1.63	2.00	7.00

Table 5 Comparison of weight and duration of fever (days) between study groups

	Study Groups	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value
Weight (Kg)	Case	34	12.65	6.52	0.003

	Control	34	17.53	6.61	
Duration of fever (days)	Case	34	5.00	1.48	0.036
	Control	34	4.17	1.69	

Table 6 Frequency distribution of residence of the patients

		Frequency	Percent
Residence	Rural	33	48.5
	Urban	35	51.5
	Total	68	100.0

Table 7 Comparison of residence of the patients between study groups

		Study Groups		Total	p-value
		Case	Control		
Residence	Rural	15	18	33	0.467
		44.1%	52.9%	48.5%	
	Urban	19	16	35	
		55.9%	47.1%	51.5%	
Total		34	34	68	
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Figure - 2 Frequency distribution of socioeconomic status

Table 8 Comparison of socioeconomic status of the patients

		Study Groups		Total	p-value
		Case	Control		
SES	Low	8	15	23	0.199
		23.5%	44.1%	33.8%	
	Middle	14	10	24	
		41.2%	29.4%	35.3%	
	High	12	9	21	
		35.3%	26.5%	30.9%	
Total		34	34	68	
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Table 9 Descriptive statistics of Hb and ferritin level of the patients

	Study Groups	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	p-value
Hb (g/dl)	Case	34	10.34	2.43	0.009
	Control	34	11.93	2.41	
Ferritin level (ng/L)	Case	34	27.08	8.95	0.023
	Control	34	32.67	10.72	

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Figure - 3 Frequency distribution of IDA of the patients

Table 10 Comparison of IDA of the patients between study groups

		Study Groups		Total	p-value	OR (CI)
		Case	Control			
IDA	Present	22	11	33	0.008	1.94 (1.16-3.26)
		64.7%	32.4%	48.5%		
	Absent	12	23	35		
		35.3%	67.6%	51.5%		
Total		34	34	68		
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		

Table 11 Comparison of IDA of the patients between study groups stratified by age (years)

Age (years)	IDA	Study Groups		Total	p-value	OR (CI)
		Case	Control			
≤ 6	Present	17	2	19	0.001	12.75 (2.29-70.96)
		68.0%	14.3%	48.7%		
Absent	Present	8	12	20		
		32.0%	85.7%	51.3%		
>6	Present	5	9	14	0.599	1.53 (0.31-7.43)
		55.6%	45.0%	48.3%		
	Absent	4	11	15		
		44.4%	55.0%	51.7%		

Table 12 Comparison of IDA of the patients between study groups stratified by gender.

Gender	IDA	Study Groups		Total	p-value	OR (CI)
		Case	Control			
Male	Present	9	4	13	0.050	5.06 (0.95-26.77)
		69.2%	30.8%	50.0%		
	Absent	4	9	13		
		30.8%	69.2%	50.0%		
Female	Present	13	7	20	0.064	3.25 (0.92-11.51)
		61.9%	33.3%	47.6%		
	Absent	8	14	22		
		38.1%	66.7%	52.4%		

Table 13 Comparison of IDA of the patients between study groups stratified by weight.

Weight (kg)	IDA	Study Groups		Total	p-value	OR (CI)
		Case	Control			
≤15	Present	17	2	19	0.001	12.75 (2.29-70.96)
		68.0%	14.3%	48.7%		
	Absent	8	12	20		
		32.0%	85.7%	51.3%		
>15	Present	5	9	14	0.599	1.53 (0.31-7.44)

		55.6%	45.0%	48.3%		
	Absent	4	11	15		
		44.4%	55.0%	51.7%		

Table 14 Comparison of IDA of the patients between study groups stratified by duration of fever.

Duration of fever	IDA	Study Groups		Total	p-value	OR (CI)
		Case	Control			
≤4	Present	11	8	19	0.069	3.78 (0.87-16.32)
		73.3%	42.1%	55.9%		
	Absent	4	11	15		
		26.7%	57.9%	44.1%		
>4	Present	11	3	14	0.026	5.50 (1.15-26.14)
		57.9%	20.0%	41.2%		
	Absent	8	12	20		

		42.1%	80.0%	58.8%		
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Table 15 Comparison of IDA of the patients between study groups stratified by residence.

Residence	IDA	Study Groups		Total	p-value	OR (CI)
		Case	Control			
Rural	Present	10	8	18	0.202	2.50 (0.60-10.34)
		66.7%	44.4%	54.5%		
	Absent	5	10	15		
		33.3%	55.6%	45.5%		
Urban	Present	12	3	15	0.008	7.43 (1.55-35.47)
		63.2%	18.8%	42.9%		
	Absent	7	13	20		
		36.8%	81.2%	57.1%		

Table 16.A. Classification of socioeconomic status of Pakistan based on monthly income.

Reference] Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2020). Household Integrated Economic Survey (HIES)

Upper socioeconomic status	Income: PKR 365,000 per month
Middle socioeconomic status	Income: PKR 70,700 per month
Lower socioeconomic status	Income: PKR 20,700 per month

Table 16.B Comparison of IDA of the patients between study groups stratified by SES.

SES	IDA	Study Groups		Total	p-value	OR (CI)
		Case	Control			
Low	Present	5	4	9	0.094	4.58 (0.73-28.64)
		62.5%	26.7%	39.1%		
	Absent	3	11	14		
		37.5%	73.3%	60.9%		
Middle	Present	7	5	12	>0.999	1.00 (0.19-5.07)
		50.0%	50.0%	50.0%		
	Absent	7	5	12		
		50.0%	50.0%	50.0%		
High	Present	10	2	12	0.005	17.50 (1.97-155.59)
		83.3%	22.2%	57.1%		
	Absent	2	7	9		
		16.7%	77.8%	42.9%		

DISCUSSION:

Febrile fits are the most frequent seizures seen in young children without any evidence of brain infection or metabolic derangement. Iron is also an important cofactor for enzymatic activity and neurochemical processes required for normal brain functioning. Iron deficiency has long been linked with all manner of neurologic outcomes in children, from learning and memory difficulties to behavioral changes and slowed cognitive development. The association between iron deficiency and febrile seizures was first described by Italian research in the mid-1990s⁹⁻¹².

This relationship has been the subject of numerous studies. For example, Vikash Lal et al. (22) evaluated a cohort of 510 pediatric patients and noted iron deficiency anemia (IDA) in 133 patients. Of these, 82 and 51 were in the case and control groups, respectively. It also revealed a strong association between IDA and febrile seizures ($p \leq 0.05$) having odds ratio (OR) of 1.608, which demonstrated that children with febrile seizures were at higher risk of developing IDA. This implies that ID might be a predisposing factor for FS in children¹.

In the same vein, Byung Ok Kwak et al. showed a strong association between IDA and febrile seizures (OR, 1.98; 95% CI, 1.26–3.13; $p = 0.003$). The study also conducted a sensitivity analysis of IDA-diagnostic value by calculating summary-receiver operating characteristic (SROC) pooled estimates of serum iron, plasma ferritin and mean corpuscular volume (MCV). The presence of IDA diagnosed according to plasma ferritin (OR, 3.78; 95% CI, 1.80–7.94; $p < 0.001$) or MCV (OR, 2.08; 95% CI, 1.36–3.17; $p = 0.001$) was moderately associated with febrile seizures [26]. In contrast, serum iron level-only-based diagnosis for IDA was not significantly associated with febrile seizures (OR: 0.57; $p = 0.210$)².

Hartified et al. (2009), febrile seizure patients had 2 times greater chance of suffering from iron deficiency compared with a control group Oil was more effective than caraway oil in the inhibition of larvae development. Furthermore, anemia was significantly more common among their patients (30%) compared to controls (14%).¹⁰ In another study done in 2001, Naveed-ur-Rehman et al. studied 30 febrile seizure cases and similar number of controls, and found a significantly higher prevalence of IDA among the former as compared to the latter.¹⁵ In the current study, IDA prevalence was 20% in case and 12% in control.¹⁶ In addition, a study suggested that children with IDA, especially those in low-to-moderate anemia prevalence areas, were at moderate risk of febrile convulsion and thereby there may be need for more prospective studies and interventional studies to improve the public health concern.⁹

In a study in the south of Iran, significant relationship found between IDA and febrile seizures with 56.6% of cases and 24.8% of controls between them, which was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).⁵ Another study from Pakistan found a significant association of iron deficiency anemia and febrile convulsions, affecting 59% cases as compared to 26% controls ($P < 0.05$).⁶

In South Korea, it was found in a study that iron deficiency (ferritin < 30 ng/mL) was more common among children who had febrile seizures (49.2%) when compared to controls (16.9%).⁷ The authors speculated that iron deficiency before the anemia may increase febrile seizure risk.

Muhammad Awais et al. found prevalence of IDA among 95 patients where 31 (16.3%) cases showed IDA [cases: 18/95 (18.9%), controls: 13/95(13.7%)] and the odds ratio

was 1.475 indicating a marginally more probability onto cases in comparison with controls although it did not reach to significant level ($P = 0.326$).¹⁷ A similar insignificant relationship, however with modest increased risk of febrile convulsions in children with IDA was shown in our study.¹⁹ The prevalence of IDA was 22 (64.7%) in the case group and 11 (32.4%) in the control group in our study. The calculated OR for IDA was 1.94 in the case group as opposed to controls, indicating that it was statistically significant ($P = 0.008$; OR = 1.94 [1.16–3.26]).

On the other hand, other studies presented contrasting findings with respect to the correlation between IDA and FS. Kobrinsky et al. reported reduced frequency of iron deficiencies for their cases and suggested that iron deficiency may have a protective effect against febrile convulsions.¹⁷ Bidabadi and Mashouf also showed that IDA was less frequent in the febrile convulsion group than controls, but they did not show any protective role for iron deficiency on simple febrile convulsions.¹⁸ Momen and Hakimzadeh reported no significant association between febrile convulsions and IDA.²⁰ Such inconsistencies could be due to variation in the diagnostic criteria of IDA, sample size and failure to adjust for age in interpretation of diagnostic tests for IDA.

The present study, however, shows a definite link and perhaps causality between iron deficiency and the initial episode of febrile seizure. It is worth to mention that prevalence of iron deficiency anemia in hospitalized children in a developing country such as Pakistan (8) is tremendously high compared with developed countries. Thus, more large-scale community-based studies are needed to better investigate the association between these two common entities.

Moreover, a number of measures for iron status including ferritin, hemoglobin, MCV and MCH/MCHC were measured in both cases and controls in the present study.

CONCLUSION:

In the light of this study, it is recommended that there is a statistically increase in risk to develop febrile convulsions among children with iron deficiency from Children who has convulsions without Iron deficiency between age (6-60) months.

REFERENCES:

- Lal V, Kumar H, Hanif S, Parkash O, Arwani S. Association of iron deficiency anemia in children with febrile convulsions. *Pakistan Journal of Neurological Sciences (PJNS)*. 2016;11(3):3-8.
- Kwak BO, Kim K, Kim S-N, Lee R. Relationship between iron deficiency anemia and febrile seizures in children: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Seizure*. 2017;52:27-34.
- Sultan T, Hanif AI, Ali S. Iron deficiency anemia as a risk factor for simple febrile seizures. *Pak J Neurol Sci*. 2017;12(3):36-40.
- Brajesh Raj C, Karmacharya Malla K, Gaire B. Association of Iron Deficiency Anemia with Febrile Seizure in Children in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Journal of Nepal Health Research Council*. 2021 Apr 23;19(1):66-70.
- Zareifar S, Hosseinzadeh HR, Cohan N. Association between iron status and febrile seizures in children. *Seizure*. 2012/10/01;21(8):603-5.
- Hussain AW, Haq AU, Shahzad S, Murtaza B, Nawaz U, Lodhi MA. IDA—a risk factor for febrile seizures in children. *Pak Armed Forces Med J*. 2018;68(5):1300-5.
- Jang HN, Yoon HS, Lee EH. Prospective case control study of iron deficiency and the risk of febrile seizures in children in South Korea. *BMC Pediatrics*. 2019/09/04;19(1):309.
- Warner MJ, Kamran MT. Iron deficiency anemia. 2017.
- Habibian N, Alipour A, Rezaianzadeh A. Association between iron deficiency anemia and febrile convulsion in 3-to 60-month-old children: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Iranian journal of medical sciences*. 2014;39(6):496.
- Pisacane A, Sansone R, Impagliazzo N, Coppola A, Rolando P, D'Apuzzo A, et al. IDA and febrile convulsions: case-control study in children under 2 years. *Bmj*. 1996;313(7053):343.
- Ohls R, Christensen R. Iron-Deficiency Anaemia. *Nelson Text book of Pediatrics*. 18th Edition on Philadelphia: Saunders. 2008:2014-7.
- Ambruso D, Hays T, Goldenberg N. IDA. *Current Diagnosis and Treatment-Paediatrics 19th Edition* Denver USA: McGraw Hill. 2009;11.
- Improvement SCoQ, Management SoFS. Febrile seizures: clinical practice guideline for the long-term management of the child with simple febrile seizures. *Pediatrics*. 2008;121(6):1281-6.
- Hartfield DS, Tan J, Yager JY, Rosychuk RJ, Spady D, Haines C, et al. The association between iron deficiency and febrile seizures in childhood. *Clinical pediatrics*. 2009;48(4):420-6.
- Billoo A. Association between iron deficiency anemia and febrile seizures. *Journal of the College of Physicians and Surgeons-pakistan: JCPSP*. 2005;15(6):338-40.
- Siadati A SF, Farivar S. . Febrile seizure and serum iron level, abstracts book of 15th international congress of pediatrics Tehran. 2003 151-3.
- Kobrinisky NL, Yager JY, Cheang MS, Yatscoff RW, Tenenbein M. Does iron deficiency raise the seizure threshold? *Journal of child neurology*. 1995;10(2):105-9.
- Bidabadi E, Mashouf M. Association between iron deficiency anemia and first febrile convulsion: a case-control study. *Seizure*. 2009;18(5):347-51.
- Awais M, Razzaq A, Ateeq S, Ullah H. ASSOCIATION OF IDA WITH FEBRILE FITS. *Journal of Postgraduate Medical Institute*. 2022;36(3):162-5.
- Moumen A, HAKIM ZM. Case-Control Study Of The Relationship Between Anemia And Febrile Convulsion In Children Between 9 Months To 5 Years. *Of Age*. 2003